

Infra/Red Investigations of Fluoroberyllates

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INFRA-RED spectra of the sulphates have been investigated^{1,2}. Little seems to have been done on the I. R. investigations of fluoroberyllates. Since chemically they are similar it would be interesting to investigate the I.R. spectra of the fluoroberyllates.

From theoretical considerations it can be shown^{3,4} that for a tetrahedral molecule like BeF_4^{-2} , we should have four normal modes of vibrations all of which are Raman active whereas only two, ν_3 and ν_4 , are infra-red active.

Experimental :

All the spectra were taken in a Perkin Elmer 421 grating instrument. All the spectra were taken in Nujol Mull with KBr or AgCl plates. All the data are given in cm^{-1} .

TABLE I

	ν_3	ν_4
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4$	790,735	480
Na_2BeF_4	850,760	490
K_2BeF_4	810,760	500
Li_2BeF_4	805,775	490
$\text{CuBeF}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	830,770	480
$\text{ZnBeF}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	800,740	485
$\text{NiBeF}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	820,760	490
$\text{CoBeF}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	800,730	480
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{CuBeF}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	850,760	490
$\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{NiBeF}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	835,760	490
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{ZnBeF}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	835,762	500
$(\text{NH}_4)\text{-Al-BeF}_4$	720	485
Cs-Al-BeF_4	735,720	485
Rb-Al-BeF_4	735,725	485
Ti-Al BeF_4	735,720	490

It is to be noticed that ν_3 vibrations are split, no doubt, due to crystal field effect. All the fluoroberyllate absorptions, specially the ν_3 absorption, are broad, but ν_4 (the angle bending) are sharp. It was found that the copper salts contained some

sulphate as impurity, hence this salt deviated from its group. The lowering of ν_3 in $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4$ may be due to hydrogen bonding⁴.

In the alum the ν_3 has shifted to lower frequency which is probably an indication of complex formation. It is to be noticed that in this case it is the ν_3 frequency that is more affected than the ν_4 one. One can see this from SO_4^{-2} .⁵

Compound	Symmetry	ν_3	ν_4
SO_4^{-2} ion	T_d	1104	613
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{2+} (\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	T_d	1130—1140 1032—1044	617 645
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{SO}_4]\text{Br}$	C_4	1117—1143	604
NH_4		1050—1060	641
$[(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$	C_2	1170	610
SO_4		1105	571

It is to be noted that because of the lowering of symmetry, number of bands increases. But we do not see such a drastic change in the alum and thus they should not be regarded as a complex. Nevertheless a tendency for complex formation is exhibited. Sulphate alums do not show such a change.

From Table I we conclude that BeF_4^{-2} ion absorbs in the region $800-725\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $480-500\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

References :

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